

EFFECT OF INCREASING LEVELS OF WET DISTILLERS GRAINS WITH SOLUBLES (WDGS) IN CROSSBRED DAIRY COW DIETS ON DIGESTION, NUTRIENT BALANCE AND MICROBIAL PROTEIN SYNTHESIS

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Abstract

As farmers of Andhra Pradesh, India in many places are using WDGS in large quantities to feed milch animals in desire of more milk, to know the effect of feeding WDGS on nutrient utilization a metabolism trial was conducted for 7 days at the end of a 120-day lactation trial, using APBN green fodder and paddy straw as roughage and concentrate mixture (T1, control) or WDGS @ 15 (T2), 25 (T3) and 35 % (T4) of DM requirement using 6 crossbred dairy cows per treatment allotted at random to one of the four dietary treatments as per ICAR, 2013 nutrient specifications. The digestibility (%) of DM, OM, CP, NFE and ADF did not differ among treatments, while significant increase in digestibility (%) of EE ($P < 0.01$), CF ($P < 0.05$), NDF ($P < 0.01$), hemicellulose ($P < 0.01$) and cellulose ($P < 0.01$) was observed with increasing levels of WDGS in the diet. The N retention expressed as g/d, % intake and % absorbed was higher ($P < 0.05$) in T4, compared to other treatments. Calcium retention (g/d) was higher ($P < 0.05$) in control group, compared to WDGS fed animals, but as % intake and as % absorbed it did not differ significantly among treatments. Phosphorus retention g/d and as % intake did not differ significantly among groups, but as % absorbed, it decreased significantly ($P < 0.01$) from 81.72 to 61.53 as the level of WDGS inclusion increased from 0 to 35%. The total purine derivative excretion in urine (mmol/kg $w^{0.75}/d$) and microbial protein supply (g/kg $w^{0.75}/d$) were significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) in T4 (1.26 and 4.68, respectively), compared to other groups. This study demonstrated that dairy cattle diets containing WDGS up to 35% of DMI resulted in improved nutrient digestibility and microbial protein synthesis.

Keywords: Crossbred cows, Digestibility, MCP synthesis, Nutrient utilisation, WDGS.

Introduction

India has huge livestock population with 193.6 million cattle and 111.8 million buffaloes (FAO, 2022), which demands the use of alternative feed resources like wet distillers grain with solubles (WDGS). The increased ethanol production from grain in recent years has resulted in increased availability of wet distillers grains with solubles (WDGS). WDGS is the main co-product of the brewing industry, accounting for about 85 per cent of total by-products released (Mussatto *et al.*, 2006) and is extensively used as energy and protein source in the cattle-feeding industry (Ponce *et al.*, 2024). WDGS is rich in protein with 1.8 times more rumen undegraded protein value than soybean meal (Zentek *et al.*, 2014) and 1.3 times the energy value of maize (Klopfenstein *et al.*, 2008). Because WDGS is relatively low in starch and high in digestible fibre, it can be used to provide dietary energy with a low risk of ruminal acidosis (Duncan *et al.*, 2024). As MCP is an important component of metabolizable protein (NRC, 2000), research probing the effect of WDGS on rumen microbial N flow is needed. Thus, the present study was undertaken to determine the effects of feeding WDGS in crossbred dairy cattle on nutrient digestibility and microbial protein synthesis.

Materials And Methods

Experimental design

The present study was conducted at Dept. of LFC and Dept. of Animal Nutrition, College of Veterinary Science, Tirupati. In a 120-day lactation study 24 lactating Jersey x Sahiwal crossbred cows (336.87 ± 9.96 kg) in late lactation (183.92 ± 2.38 days) with average milk yield of 5.55 ± 0.35 kg/d, were divided into four groups of 6 cows each and randomly allotted to one of the dietary treatments. The four dietary treatments used in the feeding trial were formulated using Hybrid Napier (APBN-1) green fodder and paddy straw as roughages and concentrate mixture (T1, control) or WDGS @ 15 % (T2), 25% (T3) and 35 % (T4) of DMI. Concentrate mixture was prepared by using maize, DORB, soybean meal, urea and mineral mixture. The experimental diets were fed depending on the body weight and level of production of animals as per ICAR (2013) recommendations. The

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cows were housed in a pucca shed with the provision for individual feeding and watering. The experimental animals had free access to clean and wholesome drinking water.

Metabolism trial was conducted using all six animals in each treatment at the end of the lactation trial for 7 days by collecting faecal grab samples and spot urine samples. Body weight of the cows was recorded before and after the end of collection period. The nutrient digestibility was estimated using Acid Detergent Insoluble Ash (Manthey *et al.*, 2016) as internal marker. Nitrogen, calcium and phosphorus balance were determined by taking the difference between intake from feed and outgo from faeces and urine. During the collection period, representative samples of feed offered and leftover feed if any were collected to estimate dry matter and pooled for 7 days for each animal. The samples of feed offered and leftover feed were ground separately in a laboratory Weily mill through a 1 mm screen and preserved in air tight bottles for subsequent analysis.

Faecal grab samples

Faecal grab samples were collected for 7 days from the rectum of all cows thrice daily and composited for individual cows. The samples collected each day were kept frozen in a deep freezer. After the end of the trial, samples collected from each animal for the seven days were pooled, mixed together and sub samples were taken for analysis. The moisture content was determined and the crude protein was estimated using the fresh samples. The rest of the analysis was done in dried and ground samples.

Estimation of urine output (UO)

Urinary creatinine was used as an alternative method of total urine collection. The total daily urine output was estimated by dividing the estimate of daily urinary excretion of creatinine with the observed values of creatinine concentration in the urine according to Valadares Filho and Valadares (2001). The creatinine concentration in urine was estimated using commercial kits (Erba test kits manufactured by Transasia Bio-medicals ltd) by Jaffe's method using spectrophotometer (Bowers, 1980). The daily urinary creatinine excretion was estimated by using 24.05 mg of creatinine per kg of

unshrunk body weight of dairy cows, and the assumption that creatinine is excreted constantly over 24 h (Chizzotti *et al.*, 2007).

Spot urine collection and processing

Spot urine samples were collected from each animal daily thrice after each milking and at night by manual stimulation of the perivulvar region and aliquots from each sampling were pooled per cow per period. Samples were acidified to avoid bacterial destruction of purine derivatives and kept at -20°C until analysed (Gehman and Kononoff, 2010a, and Gehman and Kononoff, 2010b). For estimation of purine derivatives in urine, urine was filtered through 0.22µm millipore filter paper and diluted the sample (1 ml of urine was mixed with 10 ml of distilled water) and stored in air-tight bottles and frozen in a deep freezer (IAEA TECDOC-945, 1997).

Estimation of microbial protein synthesis

Microbial protein synthesis was determined by estimating total purine derivatives (PD) excreted in urine. Purine derivative determination in cattle included analysis for uric acid and allantoin, since xanthine and hypoxanthine are present in trace quantities (IAEA TECDOC-945, 1997). Allantoin and uric acid were estimated using the colorimetric method as described in IAEA-TECDOC-945 (1997). The amount of microbial allantoin absorbed (mmol/day) corresponding to PD

excreted (mmol/day) was estimated by the formula given by Chen *et al.* (1990) and the amount of microbial nitrogen (MN g/day) supply was calculated using the procedure given by Chen and Gomes (1992).

Chemical analysis

Feed samples (concentrate mixture, WDGS, paddy straw, and APBN), orts and faecal samples were analyzed for proximate constituents and urine for N according to AOAC (2005) methods. Cell-wall constituents viz., neutral detergent fibre (NDF), acid detergent fibre (ADF), cellulose, acid detergent lignin (ADL), and acid detergent insoluble ash (ADIA) were determined for feeds and faeces by using the methods described by Van Soest *et al.* (1991). Hemi-cellulose was calculated as NDF – ADF.

Statistical analysis

The data of the study was subjected to analysis through software (version 23.0; SPSS, 2015) by applying one-way analysis of variance through generalized linear model using statistical procedures of Snedecor and Cochran (1994).

Results And Discussion

The chemical composition of WDGS and other feeds used in the experiment is given in Table 1. WDGS is high in CP and comparable with the values of Westendorf *et al.* (2014) and Durga *et al.* (2018).

Table 1. Chemical composition (%) of Experimental feeds (on DM basis)

Parameter	WDGS	Concentrate mixture	APBN	Paddy straw
Dry matter	28.22	91.55	24.77	90.70
Organic matter	94.75	89.65	89.29	85.59
Crude protein	36.72	21.83	7.31	4.44
Ether extract	8.74	1.64	2.35	1.34
Crude fibre	7.16	11.56	32.38	35.17
Total ash	5.25	10.39	10.70	14.41
Nitrogen free extract	42.12	54.60	47.25	44.63
Neutral Detergent Fibre	44.69	33.28	66.82	78.84
Acid Detergent Fibre	21.25	19.31	44.23	52.39
Hemicellulose	24.27	13.94	22.59	26.44
Cellulose	16.10	11.07	31.39	39.64
Lignin	3.69	5.54	7.31	5.40
ADIA	1.46	2.7	5.53	7.38
Calcium	0.32	0.99	1.54	0.28
Phosphorus	0.67	0.43	0.59	0.11

* Mean of four values

Apparent digestibility

The digestibility of diets for different nutrients with different levels of WDGS inclusion is presented in Table 2. Digestibility of DM, OM, CP and NFE did not differ among groups incorporated with different levels of WDGS. EE digestibility was significantly ($P<0.01$) higher in T3 and T4 than in T1 and T2. Significant increase ($P<0.05$) of crude fibre digestibility was observed in T3 (25% WDGS) and T4 (35% WDGS), compared to T1 (control) and T2 (15% WDGS). NDF digestibility increased ($P<0.01$) with the increase in the level of WDGS inclusion from 44.08 (T1) to 57.17 (T4) per cent. ADF digestibility did not differ among groups with the increase of WDGS in the diet. Higher ($P<0.01$) hemicellulose and cellulose digestibilities were observed in T3 and T4 compared to other groups. Similar to the findings of the present study non-significant differences in the digestibility of nutrients were reported by Aguilera-soto *et al.* (2009), Kelzer *et al.* (2009), and Gehman and Kononoff (2010b) for DM, OM, and CP, by Chandrika *et al.* (2021) for DM and CP, with use of distillers grains in ruminant diets. In contrast, Gehman and Kononoff (2010a) reported lower ($P<0.01$) DM digestibility in dairy cows fed 15% WDGS than in the control group without WDGS. Contrary to the present results, higher CP digestibilities were reported by Gehman and Kononoff (2010a),

Feyisa *et al.* (2015), Inthapanya *et al.* (2016) and Faccenda *et al.* (2017) by the inclusion of WDGS or DDGS in ruminant rations. Consistent with the results of EE digestibility of the present study, Hales *et al.* (2015) and Faccenda *et al.* (2017) also reported increased EE digestibility by the inclusion of WDGS or dried brewers grain in the diets of cattle. Increased ($P<0.05$) CF digestibility with the increase in the level of WDGS in the present study might be attributed to the increase ($P<0.01$) in the digestibility of NDF, hemicellulose and cellulose contents of the diet with increase in the level of WDGS. As in case of the present study, increased NDF digestibility with the inclusion of brewers grain in cattle ration was also reported by Feyisa *et al.* (2015), Faccenda *et al.* (2017), Aguilera-soto *et al.* (2009), Kelzer *et al.* (2009), Gehman and Kononoff (2010b), Ramirez *et al.* (2011) and Hales *et al.* (2015). Kononoff (2010) stated that compared to corn, WDGS/DDGS contained a higher proportion of NDF (28.9/33.1 vs. 9.76%), and is not highly lignified thus it is highly digestible. This fermentable fibre, as it is fermented in the rumen at a slower rate than starch in the rumen, keeps the pH above the sub-acute ruminal acidosis levels ($pH < 5.6$), favours the proliferation of *Selenomonas ruminantium* population, which is important to prevent acidosis (Nagaraja and Titgemeyer, 2007).

Table 2 Nutrient digestibility of lactating crossbred cows fed different levels of WDGS.

	T1	T2	T3	T4
DM				
Intake (kg)	8.65±0.42	7.78±0.46	7.40±0.23	7.73±0.65
Out go (kg)	3.76±0.19	3.65±0.28	3.31±0.23	3.34±0.30

% digestibility	56.52 ± 0.92	53.07 ± 2.46	55.27 ± 2.85	56.99 ± 1.02
OM				
Intake (kg)	7.58±0.38	6.90±0.42	6.62±0.21	6.99±0.60
Out go (kg)	3.02±0.16	2.94±0.23	2.69±0.20	2.74±0.26
% digestibility	60.18 ± 0.92	57.31 ± 2.42	59.37 ± 2.72	61.08 ± 1.01
CP				
Intake (kg)	1.14±0.07	1.13±0.10	1.18±0.06	1.45±0.16
Out go (kg)	0.43±0.02	0.43±0.03	0.46±0.04	0.54±0.07
% digestibility	61.84 ± 0.75	61.79 ± 0.95	61.57 ± 2.00	62.82 ± 1.09
EE				
Intake (kg)**	0.19 ^a ±0.01	0.25 ^{ab} ±0.02	0.29 ^b ±0.01	0.36 ^a ±0.04
Out go (kg)	0.05±0.01	0.06±0.01	0.04±0.01	0.06±0.01
% digestibility**	71.92 ^b ± 3.81	75.24 ^b ± 2.98	85.27 ^a ± 1.88	83.80 ^a ± 1.15
CF				
Intake (kg)	2.04±0.08	1.87±0.08	1.78±0.04	1.74±0.11
Out go (kg)**	1.18 ^a ±0.08	1.04 ^{ab} ±0.05	0.87 ^b ±0.07	0.85 ^b ±0.08
% digestibility*	42.34 ^b ± 1.39	44.70 ^{ab} ± 2.10	51.31 ^a ± 3.14	51.68 ^a ± 1.59
NFE				
Intake (kg)	4.21±0.22	3.65±0.22	3.37±0.11	3.44±0.24
Out go (kg)	1.41±0.08	1.37±0.14	1.31±0.10	1.28±0.12
% digestibility	66.46 ± 0.78	62.36 ± 2.82	61.33 ± 2.85	63.01 ± 1.48
NDF				
Intake (kg)	4.80±0.19	4.67±0.23	4.62±0.11	4.82±0.36
Out go (kg)	2.69±0.15	2.43±0.19	2.12±0.21	2.09±0.21
% digestibility**	44.08 ^c ± 1.37	47.97 ^{bc} ± 2.05	54.21 ^{ab} ± 1.59	57.17 ^a ± 1.58
ADF				
Intake (kg)	3.07±0.12	2.93±0.13	2.85±0.06	2.91±0.21
Out go (kg)	1.94±0.10	1.80±0.13	1.63±0.11	1.63±0.15
% digestibility	37.09 ± 1.31	38.86 ± 2.91	43.18 ± 3.15	44.63 ± 1.75
Hemicellulose				
Intake (kg)	1.73±0.07	1.73±0.10	1.77±0.05	1.91±0.16
Out go (kg)**	0.76 ^a ±0.06	0.64 ^{ab} ±0.07	0.50 ^b ±0.05	0.46 ^b ±0.06
% digestibility**	56.47 ^b ± 2.13	63.36 ^b ± 3.45	71.98 ^a ± 2.06	76.28 ^a ± 2.02
Cellulose				
Intake (kg)	2.14±0.07	2.13±0.09	2.12±0.04	2.18±0.15
Out go (kg)	1.10±0.06	0.98±0.08	0.86±0.06	0.89±0.10
% digestibility**	48.89 ^b ± 1.65	54.03 ^{ab} ± 2.59	59.75 ^a ± 2.24	59.71 ^a ± 1.85

^{abc} values in a row not sharing common superscripts differ significantly * (P<0.05), ** (P<0.01).

Nutrient balance

Non-significant differences were observed in N intake, faecal N outgo and urinary N excretion (Table.3) across different treatments fed with increasing levels of WDGS (0, 15, 25 and 35% of DM requirement), but nitrogen increase in intake and faecal excretion of N was seen in the group fed T4. Nitrogen retention (g/d) was significantly (P<0.05) higher in T4 compared to other treatments. T4 group animals showed a significant increase in N retention when expressed as % of intake (P<0.05) and as % of absorbed (P<0.01) compared to other treatments. Similar to the present study Chibisa *et al.* (2012) found non-significant differences in N intake (g/d), Urinary N excretion (g/d) and total N excretion (g/d) in dairy cows fed barley silage based TMR containing canola meal as major protein supplement (control) or diets formulated to contain 10, 15, and 20% of wheat DDGS on DM basis. Gehman and

Kononoff (2010b) reported unaffected fecal N excretion, lowered (P<0.01) urinary N, decreased total manure N (fecal + urinary N) in dairy cattle fed high corn silage or high alfalfa silage with 25% WDGS compared to control. Whereas, Spiels and Varel (2009), Gehman and Kononoff (2010a), and Hales *et al.* (2012) reported increased total N excretion in cattle fed on diets containing distillers grains. In consistence with the result of N retention of the present study, Gehman and Kononoff (2010b), Benchaar *et al.* (2013), Hales *et al.* (2015) and Inthapanya *et al.* (2016) also reported increased retention of productive N in cattle fed wet or dried distillers grains. However non-significant differences in N retention in cattle by feeding distillers grains was reported by Spiels and Varel (2009), Gehman and Kononoff (2010a) and Hales *et al.* (2012).

Table 3. Effect of Inclusion of WDGS on Nitrogen balance of crossbred cows

	T1	T2	T3	T4
N intake (g/d)	181.89 ± 11.83	181.31 ± 16.21	189.24 ± 9.47	231.25 ± 26.00
N outgo, g/d				
Faeces	59.75 ± 4.81	76.10 ± 8.88	77.67 ± 7.14	88.38 ± 10.66
Urine	83.30 ± 7.62	64.00 ± 7.77	66.60 ± 6.77	79.47 ± 6.88
Total	143.05 ± 8.70	140.10 ± 11.94	144.26 ± 6.99	167.85 ± 17.02
N balance				
Retention (g/d)*	38.83 ^b ± 3.37	41.21 ^b ± 5.01	44.97 ^b ± 4.62	63.40 ^a ± 9.32
% intake*	21.24 ^b ± 0.68	22.55 ^b ± 1.12	23.61 ^{ab} ± 1.91	26.86 ^a ± 1.30

% absorbed**	31.92 ^b ± 0.96	39.47 ^{ab} ± 2.81	40.47 ^{ab} ± 2.01	43.40 ^a ± 2.06
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^{abc} values in a row not sharing common superscripts differ significantly * (P<0.05), ** (P<0.01)

The results of calcium (Ca) and phosphorus (P) balance are presented in Table 4 and 5. Calcium intake (g/d), faecal out go (g/d) and total Ca excretion (g/d) were significantly (P<0.01) decreased with the increase in the level of WDGS from 0 to 35%. Calcium retention decreased significantly (P<0.05) from 13.66 g/d (T1-0% WDGS) to 9.74 g/d (T4-

35% WDGS). But as percent of intake or percent absorbed Ca retention did not differ significantly among groups. In consistent to the results of the study Suarez-Mena *et al.* (2019) also found a linear decrease (P<0.01) in intake of calcium (53.71-43.79 g/d), faecal excretion of Ca (38.82- 32.11 g/d) and a non-significant difference in Ca absorption and retention in dairy heifers with increasing level of DDGS (0, 7, 14 and 21% of DM).

Table 4. Calcium balance of lactating crossbred cows fed WDGS

	T1	T2	T3	T4
Ca intake (g/d)**	76.31 ^a ± 5.04	62.35 ^b ± 4.30	53.15 ^b ± 2.35	50.30 ^b ± 4.37
Ca outgo (g/d)				
Feces**	56.29 ^a ± 3.44	45.46 ^b ± 2.94	37.16 ^c ± 1.58	33.06 ^c ± 2.70
Urine	6.37 ± 0.34	6.80 ± 0.74	6.21 ± 0.98	7.49 ± 1.23
Total**	62.66 ^a ± 3.30	51.92 ^b ± 3.79	43.90 ^{bc} ± 2.00	40.56 ^c ± 3.57
Ca balance				
Retention (g/d)*	13.66 ^a ± 2.02	10.43 ^{ab} ± 1.06	9.24 ^b ± 0.76	9.74 ^b ± 1.01
% intake	17.53 ± 1.43	16.79 ± 1.53	17.38 ± 1.09	19.27 ± 1.17
% absorbed	66.83 ± 3.32	60.14 ± 4.57	60.57 ± 4.90	56.90 ± 3.95

^{abc} values in a row not sharing common superscripts differ significantly * (P<0.05), ** (P<0.01)

In the present study no differences were observed in P intake (g/d), faecal and total P excretion, but urinary P excretion increased (P<0.01) from T1 (1.73 g/d) to T4 (4.52 g/d). P retention (g/d) and retention as % intake values were not significantly different among treatments. P retention as % absorbed decreased with the inclusion of WDGS significantly (P<0.01) from 81.72 to 61.53 in T1 to T4, respectively. Similar to the urinary excretion of P (g/d) of the present study, Spiels and Varel (2009) also reported increased (P<0.01) P excretion through urine and similar apparent P retention (g/d) with the increase in the

level of WDGS from 0 to 60% in the diets of cattle. In another study, Benchaar *et al.* (2013) reported increased (P<0.001) excretion of P in faeces and urine resulted in decreased P retention with increasing levels of DDGS supplementation in cattle. In contrary, Suarez-Mena *et al.* (2019) found linear decrease (P < 0.01) in intake of P (14.64-9.26g/d) and fecal excretion P (13.78 – 8.79) with increasing levels of DDGS (0, 7, 14 and 21%) in low forage and high forage diets of dairy heifers.

Table 5. Phosphorus balance of lactating crossbred cows fed WDGS

	T1	T2	T3	T4
P intake (g/d)	31.34 ± 2.08	31.72 ± 2.60	32.11 ± 1.40	36.79 ± 3.81
P outgo, g/d				
Faeces	21.48 ± 1.63	22.33 ± 2.02	22.31 ± 1.29	24.54 ± 2.85
Urine**	1.73 ^c ± 0.26	2.75 ^b ± 0.14	3.46 ^b ± 0.34	4.52 ^a ± 0.33
Total	23.20 ± 1.40	25.09 ± 2.15	25.77 ± 1.20	29.06 ± 2.97
P balance				
Retention (g/d)	8.14 ± 0.77	6.64 ± 0.54	6.33 ± 0.26	7.73 ± 1.17
% intake	25.78 ± 1.05	21.04 ± 1.01	19.76 ± 0.55	20.77 ± 2.00
% absorbed**	81.72 ^a ± 3.34	70.40 ^b ± 1.02	65.00 ^{bc} ± 1.90	61.53 ^c ± 3.78

^{abc} values in a row not sharing common superscripts differ significantly ** (P<0.01)

Microbial protein synthesis

The data on purine derivative excretion and microbial protein supply are given in Table 6. The total urinary excretion of purine derivatives (mmol/d) did not differ significantly among different treatments, but when it is expressed per kg metabolic body weight (mmol/kg w^{0.75}/d), significant (P<0.05) increase was noticed in T4 compared to other groups. Non-significant differences were observed in urinary allantoin (mmol/d) excretion among treatments. Significant increase (P<0.01) in excretion of uric acid (mmol/d) in T3 and T4 was observed compared to T1 and T2. When expressed per kg metabolic weight (mmol/kg w^{0.75}/d) both allantoin and uric acid excretion was higher (P<0.05) in T4 compared to other groups. The mean values of estimated microbial nitrogen supply (g/d) and microbial protein supply (g/d) were not significantly different among treatments, but T4 group had higher (P<0.05) microbial nitrogen and microbial protein supply (g/kg

w^{0.75}/d), compared to other groups. Microbial protein supply (g/ kg DOMR) ranged between 92.51 and 132.62, and the value for T4 group is significantly higher (P<0.01) than that of other groups.

Similarly, increased excretion of urinary purine derivatives and microbial crude protein synthesis was reported by Gehman and Kononoff, 2010a (P<0.05) and Gehman and Kononoff, 2010b (P<0.01) in dairy cattle fed diets containing 15% WDGS and 25% WDGS, respectively compared to control diets. Chibisa *et al.* (2012) reported non-significant differences in the omasal flow of total bacterial non ammonia N and microbial efficiency (g of total bacterial N flow/kg of OM truly digested in rumen) in cattle fed iso-nitrogenous diets containing increasing amounts (0, 10, 15 and 20 % of DM) of wheat DDGS in barley silage based TMR. In contrary, Faccenda *et al.* (2017) reported a linear decrease (P<0.05) in urinary allantoin, uric acid, total purine and microbial CP in lactating dairy cows fed 50:50

forage:concentrate diets containing dried brewers grain (0,25,50, 75 & 100%) as a replacement for soybean meal.

Further the increased microbial protein supply (g/kg DOMR) may be attributed to the increased quantity of metabolizable protein (MP) due to inclusion of WDGS, conversion of excess metabolizable protein (MP) in to urea by cattle, which is potentially recycled to the rumen

and can serve as a source of DIP (Stalker *et al.*, 2007). It can be also supported that the starch from corn replaced by NDF from WDGS, reduced starch content has been shown to increase rumen pH (Oba and Allen, 2003), and increasing rumen pH from low and acidic levels has been shown to stimulate MCP synthesis (Calsamiglia *et al.*, 2008).

Table 6. Urinary excretion of purine derivatives and microbial protein supply in lactating crossbred cows fed WDGS

Parameter	T1	T2	T3	T4
Urinary excretion of purine derivatives				
<i>Allantoin</i>				
mmol/d	73.96 ± 4.75	74.32 ± 4.61	76.83 ± 5.90	89.48 ± 6.36
mmol/kg w ^{0.75} /d*	0.93 ^b ± 0.04	0.96 ^b ± 0.06	0.93 ^b ± 0.04	1.13 ^a ± 0.08
<i>Uric acid</i>				
mmol/d**	8.07 ^b ± 0.41	7.57 ^b ± 0.35	9.77 ^a ± 0.58	9.98 ^a ± 0.58
mmol/kg w ^{0.75} /d*	0.10 ^c ± 0.01	0.10 ^{bc} ± 0.01	0.12 ^{ab} ± 0.01	0.13 ^a ± 0.01
<i>Total purine derivatives</i>				
mmol/d	82.04 ± 4.97	81.90 ± 4.92	86.60 ± 6.37	99.46 ± 6.84
mmol/kg w ^{0.75} /d*	1.03 ^b ± 0.04	1.06 ^b ± 0.06	1.05 ^b ± 0.04	1.26 ^a ± 0.09
Purine absorption				
mmol/d	60.46 ± 4.67	61.15 ± 5.19	64.83 ± 6.11	80.84 ± 7.73
mmol/kg w ^{0.75} /d*	0.76 ^b ± 0.05	0.79 ^b ± 0.07	0.79 ^b ± 0.05	1.03 ^a ± 0.10
Microbial nitrogen supply				
g/d	43.95 ± 3.39	44.45 ± 3.77	47.13 ± 4.45	58.77 ± 5.61
g/kg w ^{0.75} /d*	0.55 ^b ± 0.04	0.58 ^b ± 0.05	0.57 ^b ± 0.04	0.75 ^a ± 0.07
Microbial protein supply				
g/d	274.71 ± 21.22	277.83 ± 23.58	294.55 ± 27.79	367.32 ± 35.11
g/kg w ^{0.75} /d*	3.47 ^b ± 0.23	3.60 ^b ± 0.32	3.57 ^b ± 0.22	4.68 ^a ± 0.47
g/ kg DOMR**	92.51 ^b ± 3.91	108.21 ^b ± 4.79	115.09 ^b ± 8.20	132.62 ^a ± 7.78

^{abc} values in a row not sharing common superscripts differ significantly * (P<0.05), ** (P<0.01)

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that inclusion of WDGS in dairy cattle diets improved digestibility of fibre components and calculated MCP synthesis and WDGS can be included up to 35% of dry matter intake in dairy cattle diets.

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